

Histomorphological and Histomorphometrical Postnatal Development of the Retina in White Rabbits (*Oryctolagus Cuniculus*)

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Abstract:

The present study aims to elucidate retinal development by analyzing the histomorphological and histomorphometrical parameters in white rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus* retina). Samples were collected from 25 rabbits divided into five different age groups: 1, 10, 15, 30, and 40 postnatal days (PND). The samples were then sectioned, processed, and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin stain, as well as Masson's trichrome stain. Some sections were additionally stained with toluidine blue (TB) stain to detect cell density in the outer and inner nuclear layers. Measurements of retinal layers were performed for morphometric comparison among the age groups. The findings

revealed that the total thickness of the retina gradually decreased with age. The thickness of the inner and outer nuclear layers, as well as cellular density, also decreased with the development of the photoreceptor layer (rods and cones). This decrement was accompanied by an elevation of the outer plexiform layer thickness and swelling of the ganglion cell layer, particularly after the opening of the eyelids and the differentiation of the different layers of the retina. The histomorphometry results in the retina showed significant differences in the thickness of its different layers among the five age groups. In conclusion, Retina showed highly active histological development and growth with cellular differentiation and significant measurements differences before and after eyelid opening between 10 -15 PNDs.

Keywords: *histomorphology, oryctolagus cuniculus, postnatal development, retinal development.*

Introduction

The retina, as the innermost layer of the eye, develops through two fundamental sublayers derived from the inner and outer layers of the embryonic optic cup (Schafer et al., 2018). Comprising ten tissue layers, the retina includes the retinal pigment epithelium, layer of rods and cones, external limiting membrane, outer nuclear layer, outer plexiform layer, inner nuclear layer, inner plexiform layer, ganglion cell layer, nerve fiber layer, and internal limiting membrane

(Eurell & Frappier, 2013). Rabbit eyes are commonly utilized in experiments and the evaluation of ophthalmic drugs. Therefore, comprehending the histological development of the eye can help identify critical stages and understand the effects of tissue differentiation caused by drug administration (Yamagiwa et al., 2021) Rabbit eyes also serve as an excellent model for evaluating drugs used in intraocular and retinal diseases due to their ease of handling, cost-effectiveness compared to other animals, and their similarity in size to the human eye (Ahn

et al., 2016). The rabbit's retinal model has been used in recent studies focused on growth and differentiation. It provides an accurate and relatively simple model for studying the central nervous system since the retina develops as an extension of the CNS and shares immunological and biochemical properties similar to those found in the brain and spinal cord (London et al., 2013).

Furthermore, the rabbit's retinal model is employed in various pathological studies, including research on photoreceptor layer degeneration and age-related macular degeneration (Muraoka et al., 2012), as well as investigations into retinal detachment associated with functional and anatomical changes (Barliya et al., 2017). Additionally, it is used to study subretinal hemorrhage and retinotoxicity (Bhisitkul et al., 2008). Furthermore, retinal models used in retinal surgical researches for surgical implantation technique and subretinal prostheses (Xiao et al., 2019). The present study was motivated by the absence of sufficient information regarding the histomorphological and histomorphometric development of the rabbit retina, despite the attention given to these aspects by numerous researchers in different animal species. The aim of this study is to demonstrate the histomorphological and histomorphometric development of the retina in white rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) after birth.

Materials and Methods

Twenty-five healthy white rabbits were used in this study and were obtained from animal House, College of Veterinary Medicine, Mosul University, Iraq. Regardless of their sex, animals were divided into five different age groups at 1, 10, 15, 30, 40 postnatal days (PNDs). The animals euthanized before killing according to the ethical guidelines that were approved according to American veterinary medical association (AVMA, 2020) Eyes and eyelids were excised using fine surgical tools and placed into physiological saline for the cleaning them from blood and tissue debris then were immersed into Davidson's fixative prepared according to Shariati (Shariati et al., 2008) for 24 hours and to

ensure rapid penetration. Caudal part of eye was injected with the same fixative above. The fixative was changed in the next day with 10% neutral buffer formalin and was kept for 48 hours.

The Samples were washed, cut, and were dehydrated in ascending series of graded alcohol concentrations 70, 80, 90, 100% for 2 hours each stage, later they were cleared with xylene for 30 minutes then were infiltrated with melted paraffin 58°C for 3 hours and casted into blocks, 5 micrometers thick sections were achieved using a rotary microtome (WESWOX ,MT-1090A, India) and were mounted on glass slides, sections stained with Harries Hematoxylin and eosin stain according to the protocol of Bancroft (Bancroft et al., 2019) and Masson's trichrome stain, then they were examined under the light microscope (Olympus-Dm-CBAD, Japan) for routine histological assessments, and for histomorphometric evaluation. Other sections were stained with toluidine blue for detection of cells density at outer and inner nuclear layer through retina at different age groups (Hladik & Carson, 2009).

Histomorphometric procedure

The Measurements performed to compare some parameters among groups using a 2.0 USB digital camera (scope image 9) provided with image processing software, parameters include the total thickness of retina, thickness of the whole retinal layers

Statistical analysis

Data from each group was calculated to obtain the mean and the standard error followed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan post hoc test to understand statistical differences among groups using IBM SPSS version 25.0 software at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results

The retina consisted of 10 layers, starting from the outside inward. The first layer was the inner limiting membrane, followed by the nerve fiber layer. Next was the ganglion cell layer, and then the inner plexiform layer, which represented the

synapses between bipolar neurons and ganglion cell dendrites. After that was the inner nuclear layer, which consisted of closely packed bipolar neurons, amacrine cells, and horizontal cells. These were followed by the outer plexiform layer, which was composed of synapses between the axons of the photoreceptors and the dendrites of bipolar neurons. Next the outer nuclear layer, located at the bottom, which consisted of the bodies of photoreceptor cells. Lastly, there was the layer of rods and cones, which consisted of the inner and outer segments.

The thickness of the retina on the first postnatal day (PND) measured $195.0 \pm 1.30 \mu\text{m}$ due to its relatively thick layers, especially the inner and outer nuclear layers. However, as the eyelids opened, these layers started to gradually decrease in thickness. The outer plexiform layer at first PND was extremely thin, making it challenging to distinguish the inner and outer segments of the rods and cones due to their delicate structure.

The ganglion cell layer appeared small in size, characterized by a spherical nucleus surrounded by a small amount of cytoplasm and Nissl granules. On the other hand, the layer of nerve fibers was thin and not fully developed yet, as depicted in Fig. (1A).

In the second group of animals, the retina thickness decreased to $148.9 \pm 0.33 \mu\text{m}$. This reduction was accompanied by a decrease in the thickness of the outer and inner nuclear layers. At the same time, there was noticeable progress in the development of the inner and outer segments of the rods and cones layer.

Furthermore, the thickness of the outer plexiform layer and the layer of retinal pigmented epithelium increased in comparison to the first group, Fig (1B) and Fig (3B). Additionally, the ganglion cells appeared to be more swollen.

The thickness of the retina continued to decrease in the animals of the third group until it reached $137.9 \pm 0.58 \mu\text{m}$ at 15 PND. This decrease was accompanied by the development of the photoreceptor layer and a noticeable reduction in the thickness and cell density of the inner and outer nuclear layers. Moreover, there

was an enlargement of ganglion cells with a wider cytoplasmic volume, and the nerve fiber layer expanded, Fig (1C) and Fig (2).

Figure 1. Microphotograph of Retinal Sections Illustrated the Histological Development of Retina in Different Ages Groups

Note: Postnatal day 1 (A), photoreceptor layer (asterisk). Postnatal day 10(B) Postnatal day 15(C), Postnatal day 30(D, Postnatal day 40 (E) inner limiting membrane (asterisk). Rod and cons (RC), outer nuclear layer (ONL), outer plexiform layer (OPL), inner nuclear layer (INL), inner plexiform layer (IPL) ganglionic cells layer (GCL), Nerve fibers layer (NFL). (H&E, X400).

In contrast, the animals in the fourth group, at 30 PND, exhibited elongation of the outer and inner segments of the photoreceptor layer, along with the development of the outer limiting membrane. This membrane became clearly

visible between the outer nuclear and outer plexiform layers.

Simultaneously, there was a decrease in the thickness of the outer and inner nuclear layers, as well as a reduction in cell density. On the other hand, the thickness of the inner plexiform layer showed a significant increase. Additionally, there was an increase in the thickness of the ganglion cell layer, accompanied by the enlargement of their cells and an elevation in the thickness of the nerve fiber layer, Fig (1D)

Figure 2. Microphotograph of Retina Illustrated the Histological Layers Differentiation

Note: at first PND (A), at 15 PND after eyelid opening (B), sclera (SC), choroid (Ch), Rod and cons (RC), outer nuclear layer (ONL), outer plexiform layer (OPL), inner nuclear layer (INL), inner plexiform layer (IPL) ganglionic cells layer (GCL), nerve fibers layer (NFL). (Masson's trichrome stain, X400).

The overall thickness of the retina continued to decrease gradually, reaching its lowest level at 40 PND, measuring $105.6 \pm 1.01 \mu\text{m}$. During this stage, there was a slight thinning of the nuclear layers, along with significant development of the rod and cone cells.

Furthermore, the growth and differentiation of cells in the various layers of the retina were complete, making them more similar to the retina in the eyes of adult animals, as depicted in Fig. (1E) and Fig (3A). The histomorphometric study revealed statistically significant differences in the thickness of the retina and its different layers among the different age groups (Table 1 and Figure 4) at a p-value of ≤ 0.05 .

Figure 3. Microphotograph of Retina at Illustrated the Cellular Density of Inner and Outer Nuclear Layers of Retina

Note: at 40 PND (A), at 10 PND (B), inner nuclear layer (I), outer nuclear layer (O). (toluidine blue stain, X100).

Table 1. The micro-morphometric parameters of Retina at different age groups

Variables	Post Natal Day (mean \pm SE)				
	PND 1	PND 10	PND 15	PND 30	PND 40
Rod and Cons layer thickness (μm)	5.4 ± 0.43^A	18.4 ± 0.43^B	22.6 ± 0.41^C	28.7 ± 0.24^D	32.7 ± 0.77^E
Outer nuclear layer thickness (μm)	65.7 ± 0.29^A	42.2 ± 0.42^B	38.8 ± 0.44^C	26.8 ± 0.58^D	21.5 ± 0.19^E
Outer plexiform layer thickness (μm)	5.9 ± 0.32^A	11.2 ± 0.50^B	7.9 ± 0.23^C	7.2 ± 0.13^C	6.8 ± 0.18^{AC}
Inner nuclear layer thickness (μm)	72.6 ± 0.26^A	27.2 ± 0.37^B	25.3 ± 0.33^C	18.6 ± 0.16^D	16.6 ± 0.40^E
Inner plexiform layer thickness (μm)	19.1 ± 0.41^A	25.6 ± 0.25^B	25.9 ± 0.20^C	27.9 ± 0.34^D	30.3 ± 0.42^E
Ganglionic cells layer thickness (μm)	16.3 ± 0.21^A	19.1 ± 0.72^B	15.5 ± 0.18^A	12.5 ± 0.32^C	12.3 ± 0.21^C
Total Retinal thickness (μm)	195.0 ± 1.30^A	148.9 ± 0.33^B	137.9 ± 0.58^C	125.4 ± 0.60^D	105.6 ± 1.01^E

Different letters among age in row indicate statistical significant differences at $P \leq 0.05$.

Figure 4. The micro-morphometric parameters of Retina at different age groups

Discussion

The results of the current study highlight the developmental histological changes that occur in the retina. It was observed that the thickness of the retina starts decreasing from the first day after birth and continues to decrease until the last day of the study. Moreover, there was a decrease in mitotic activity, indicating that cell division becomes less frequent, while the process of cell differentiation in the different retinal layers becomes highly active.

These findings align with a previous study (Reichenbach et al., 1991), which also reported a continuous decrease in retinal thickness after birth until puberty. The study divided the periods of cell division into two phases: the first phase ending shortly after birth, and the second phase continuing until the first month. In the second phase, simple cell divisions were observed in some cells in the inner plexiform layer, mainly limited to Müller supporting cells.

Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into the dynamic changes occurring in the developing retina and contribute to our understanding of retinal development during early postnatal stages.

The observed changes in the retinal layers during the study revealed several important findings. Firstly, there was a continuous decrease in the thickness of the inner and outer nuclear layers, accompanied by a decrease in cellular density. This reduction was particularly prominent after the opening of the eyelids. On the other hand, the outer plexiform layer showed a continuous increase in thickness until 15 PND, following the eyelid opening.

Additionally, the photoreceptor layer, which consists of rods and cones, exhibited a continuous increase in thickness throughout the study duration. The appearance of the outer limiting membrane was observed between 30 to 40 PNDs. The ganglion cell layer appeared swollen, with a decrease in the number of cells, while the thickness of the nerve fibers layer decreased.

These results correspond with previous studies. (Parker & Picut, 2016) reported that the rat's inner and outer nuclear layers are initially thick with a high cellular density at 4-6 PNDs. They also mentioned that the outer and inner plexiform layers, as well as the layer of photoreceptors, thicken soon after the opening of the eyes. Furthermore, (Heavner & Pevny, 2012) supports the finding that the thinning of the retina is primarily due to the decrease in the thickness of the inner and outer nuclear layers. They noted that cell division in both nuclear layers ceases shortly after birth in rabbits. Moreover, the thickness of the outer plexiform layer and the layer of nerve fibers increases, which corresponds to the fact that rabbits gain vision after the opening of their eyelids.

Horsburgh & Sefton (1987) found that the layer of nerve fibers is thicker after birth compared to adult animals. In contrast, the thickness of the ganglion cell layer significantly decreases and becomes reduced to one or two layers during the first week after birth. This reduction in thickness is attributed to programmed cell death, a natural process during development.

Moreover, (3) confirmed that the outer limiting membrane becomes observable around the age

of 18-20 PND. Additionally, there is an increase in the thickness of the retinal pigment epithelium layer during this period. The author emphasized that the opening of the eyelids plays a vital role in the decrease in cellular density and thickness observed in most retinal layers.

Conclusion

The findings of the study on retinal development in white rabbits demonstrated highly active histological growth and significant morphological differentiation. The observed histomorphological responses varied at different stages, particularly before and after the opening of the eyes. These results provide valuable and precise data on the developmental milestones during the postnatal life.

Furthermore, these findings suggest that the course of retinal development in white rabbits follows a similar pattern as seen in other domestic animals. This similarity highlights the relevance and applicability of the study's approach in understanding retinal development across different species.

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Conflict of interests

Authors declared that there is no conflict of interests.

References

Ahn, S.J., Hong, H.K., Na, Y.M., Park, S.J., Ahn, J., Oh, J., Woo, S.J. (2016). Use of rabbit eyes in pharmacokinetic studies of intraocular drugs. *Journal of visualized experiments: JoVE*, (113). <https://doi.org/10.3791%2F53878>

AVMA. (2020). AVMA Guidelines for the Euthanasia of Animals. Edition and general

comments. Retrieved from <https://www.avma.org/sites/default/files/2020-02/Guidelines-on-Euthanasia-2020.pdf>

Bancroft, J.D., Suvarna, K. & Christopher, L. (2019). Tissue processing. In: *Theory and practice of histological techniques*. Elsevier health sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2015-0-00143-5>

Barliya, T., Ofri, R., Sandalon, S., Weinberger, D., & Livnat, T. (2017). Changes in retinal function and cellular remodeling following experimental retinal detachment in a rabbit model. *Journal of Ophthalmology*, 2017, 4046597. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/4046597>

Bhisitkul, R.B., Winn, B.J., Lee, O.T., Wong, J., de Souza Pereira, D., Porco, T. C. & Dunaief, J. L. (2008). Neuroprotective effect of intravitreal triamcinolone acetonide against photoreceptor apoptosis in a rabbit model of subretinal hemorrhage. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*, 49(9), 4071-4077. <https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.08-1892>

Carson, F.L., & Hladik, C. (2009). *Histotechnology: A self-instructional text*. Boston: American Society for Clinical Pathology.

Eurell, J.A., & Frappier, B. L. (Eds.). (2013). *Eye. In Dellmann's textbook of veterinary histology*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.

Heavner, W., & Pevny, L. (2012). Eye development and retinogenesis. *Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in biology*, 4(12), a008391. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a008391>

Horsburgh, G.M., & Sefton, A.J. (1987). Cellular degeneration and synaptogenesis in the developing retina of the rat. *Journal of Comparative Neurology*, 263(4), 553-566. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cne.902630407>

London, A., Benhar, I., & Schwartz, M. (2013). The retina as a window to the brain—from eye research to CNS disorders. *Nature Reviews Neurology*, 9(1), 44-53. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrneurol.2012.227>

Muraoka, Y., Ikeda, H. O., Nakano, N., Hangai, M., Toda, Y., Okamoto-Furuta, K., ... & Yoshimura, N. (2012). Real-time imaging of rabbit retina with retinal degeneration by using spectral-domain optical coherence tomography.

PloS one, 7(4), e36135.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0036135>

Parker, G. A., & Picut, C. A. (Eds.). (2016). The eye and Haderian Gland. In: *Atlas of histology of the juvenile rat*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.

Reichenbach, A., Schnitzer, J., Friedrich, A., Ziegert, W., Brückner, G., & Schober, W. (1991). Development of the rabbit retina: I. Size of eye and retina, and postnatal cell proliferation. *Anatomy and embryology*, 183, 287-297.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00192216>

Schafer, K. A., Turner, O. C., & Altschuler, R. A. (2018). Special senses: eye and ear. In *Toxicologic Pathology*. CRC Press, 1133-1174.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809841-7.00022-8>

Shariati, A., Ameri, H., Hinton, D.R., & Humayun, M. S. (2008). The Effects of Davidson's Fixative Solution in Preserving the Rabbit Eye. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science*, 49(13), 5207-5207.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ieop.12119>

Xiao, Y., Wang, Y., Li, F., Lin, T., Huffman, K., Landeros, S., Cheng, L. (2019). Acute Rabbit Eye Model for Testing Subretinal Prostheses. *Translational vision science & technology*, 8(5), 20-30.
<https://doi.org/10.1167/tvst.8.5.20>

Yamagiwa, Y., Kurata, M., & Satoh, H. (2021). Histological features of postnatal development of the eye in white rabbits. *Toxicologic Pathology*, 49(3), 419-437.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0192623320915460>